

Some results for the generalized Beta function using N - fractional calculus

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Abstract.

In this paper, some results for the generalized Beta function are derived by using N -fractional calculus of the logarithm function . Also, some results associated with the usual Beta function are obtained as special cases of the main results.

Keywords: N - Fractional Calculus Operator; Generalized Beta function; Logarithm function.

1. Introduction

We adopt the following definition of fractional calculus :

Definition 1.1. (by K. Nishimoto [2])

Let $D = \{ D_-, D_+ \}$, $C = \{ C_-, C_+ \}$, C_- be a curve along the cut joining two points z and $-\infty$, C_+ be a curve along the cut joining two points z and $-\infty + i \operatorname{Im}(z)$, D_- be a domain surrounded by C_- , D_+ is a domain surrounded by C_+ (Here D contains the points over the curve C).

Moreover , let $f = f(z)$ be a regular function in $D(z \in D)$

$$f_v(z) = (f)_v = {}_c(f)_v = \frac{\Gamma(v+1)}{2\pi i} \int_c \frac{f(\zeta) d\zeta}{(\zeta-z)^{v+1}} \quad (v \notin \mathbb{Z}^-), \quad (1.1)$$

and

$$(f)_{-m} = \lim_{v \rightarrow -m} (f)_v \quad (m \in \mathbb{Z}^+), \quad (1.2)$$

where

$$-\pi \leq \arg(\zeta - z) \leq \pi \text{ for } C_- \text{ and } 0 \leq \arg(\zeta - z) \leq 2\pi \text{ for } C_+,$$

$$(\zeta \neq z), \quad z \in \mathbb{C}, v \in \mathbb{R}; \Gamma : \text{Gamma function,}$$

then $(f)_v$ is the fractional differintegration of arbitrary order v (derivatives of order v for $v > 0$ and integrals of order $-v$ for $v < 0$) with respect to z of the function f , if $|(f)_v| < \infty$.

On the fractional calculus operator N^ν , we recall the following theorems [3] :

Theorem 1.1. Let fractional calculus operator (Nishimoto's Operator) N^ν be

$$N^\nu = \left(\frac{\Gamma(\nu + 1)}{2\pi i} \int_c \frac{d\zeta}{(\zeta - z)^{\nu+1}} \right) \quad (\nu \notin Z^-), \quad (\text{Refer to [2]}) \quad (1.3)$$

$$\text{With } N^{-m} = \lim_{\nu \rightarrow -m} N^\nu \quad (m \in Z^+), \quad (1.4)$$

and define the binary operation \circ as

$$N^\beta \circ N^\alpha f = N^\beta N^\alpha f = N^\beta (N^\alpha f) \quad (\alpha, \beta \in R), \quad (1.5)$$

$$\text{then the set } \{N^\nu\} = \{N^\nu ; \nu \in R\} \quad (1.6)$$

is an Abelian product group (having continuous index ν) which has the inverse transform operator $(N^\nu)^{-1} = N^{-\nu}$ to the fractional calculus operator N^ν , for the function f such that $f \in F = \{f; 0 \neq |f_\nu| < \infty, \nu \in R\}$, where $f = f(z)$

and $z \in \mathbb{C}$. (vis. $-\infty < \nu < \infty$).

(For our convenience, we call $N^\beta \circ N^\alpha$ as product of N^β and N^α).

Theorem 1.2. The set " F.O.G. $\{N^\nu : \nu \in R\}$ " is an action product group which has continuous index ν " for the set of F . (F.O.G. Fractional calculus operator group).

Theorem 1.3.

$$\text{Let } S := \{\pm N^\nu\} \cup \{0\} = \{N^\nu\} \cup \{-N^\nu\} \cup \{0\} \quad (\nu \in R) \quad (1.7)$$

then the set S is a commutative ring for the function $f \in F$ when the identity

$$N^\alpha + N^\beta = N^\gamma \quad (N^\alpha, N^\beta, N^\gamma \in S) \quad (1.8)$$

holds[4].

Further, we recall that the generalized Beta function of n ($n \in Z^+ \geq 2$) elements (n -dimensional or n -variables) is defined by [1]

$${}_n B(\alpha_k) = B(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n) := \frac{\prod_{k=1}^n \Gamma(\alpha_k)}{\Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k)}, \quad (1.9)$$

$$(|\Gamma(\alpha_k)|, |\Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k)| < \infty).$$

where α_k ($k = 1, 2, \dots, n$ ($n \in Z^+ \geq 2$)) are variables with order number k .

We note the following special case :

$${}_2 B(\alpha_k) = B(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) = B(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) \quad (1.10)$$

where $B(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)$ is the usual Beta functions [5].

Recently, Miyakoda and Nishimoto [1] derived some identities of the generalized Beta function by using N - fractional calculus of the power function $(z - c)^{-1}$. This paper is a further attempt in introducing certain results of the generalized Beta function by employing the technique of the fractional differintegration to the logarithm function $\log(z - c)$.

2. Main results

In the following

$$\varphi = \log(z - c) \quad (z - c \neq 0), \quad (2.1)$$

we prove the following results by using N - fractional calculus :

Theorem 2.1.

We have the identity

$$\frac{\prod_{k=1}^n (\varphi_{1\alpha_k} \cdot \varphi_{2\alpha_k} \cdots \varphi_{r\alpha_k})}{\varphi_{\sum_{k=1}^n (1\alpha_k + 2\alpha_k + \cdots + r\alpha_k)}} = (-1)^{rn-1} {}_nB(1\alpha_k) {}_nB(2\alpha_k) \cdots {}_nB(r\alpha_k) \\ \times B(\sum_{k=1}^n 1\alpha_k, \sum_{k=1}^n 2\alpha_k, \dots, \sum_{k=1}^n r\alpha_k), \quad (2.2)$$

where

$$|\Gamma(1\alpha_k)|, |\Gamma(2\alpha_k)|, \dots, |\Gamma(r\alpha_k)| < \infty, \left| \Gamma\left(\sum_{k=1}^n (1\alpha_k + 2\alpha_k + \cdots + r\alpha_k)\right) \right| < \infty,$$

$$|\Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n 1\alpha_k)|, |\Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n 2\alpha_k)|, \dots, |\Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n r\alpha_k)| < \infty \text{ and } 1\alpha_k, 2\alpha_k, \dots, r\alpha_k$$

($r, k=1,2,\dots, n \in Z^+, n \geq 2$) are variables (constants for special case) with order number k .

Proof

Operating $N^{1\alpha_k}$ to the both sides of (2.1), we have

$$N^{1\alpha_k} \varphi = N^{1\alpha_k} \log(z - c),$$

that is

$$\varphi_{1\alpha_k} = (\log(z - c))_{1\alpha_k} \quad (2.3)$$

which on using the following identity [2]:

$$(\log(z - c))_{\alpha} = -e^{-i\pi\alpha} \Gamma(\alpha) (z - c)^{-\alpha} \quad (|\Gamma(\alpha)| < \infty), \quad (2.4)$$

in the r. h. s. of (2.3), gives

$$\varphi_{1\alpha_k} = -e^{-i\pi 1\alpha_k} \Gamma(1\alpha_k) (z - c)^{-1\alpha_k} \quad (|\Gamma(1\alpha_k)| < \infty), \quad (2.5)$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \prod_{k=1}^n \varphi_{1\alpha_k} &= \prod_{k=1}^n (-1)^k \cdot \prod_{k=1}^n e^{-i\pi \cdot 1\alpha_k} \prod_{k=1}^n (z-c)^{-1\alpha_k} \prod_{k=1}^n \Gamma(1\alpha_k) \\ &= (-1)^n e^{-i\pi \sum_{k=1}^n 1\alpha_k} \cdot (z-c)^{-\sum_{k=1}^n 1\alpha_k} \prod_{k=1}^n \Gamma(1\alpha_k) \quad (n \in Z^+, n \geq 2). \end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

In the same way, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \prod_{k=1}^n \varphi_{2\alpha_k} &= \prod_{k=1}^n (-1)^k \cdot \prod_{k=1}^n e^{-i\pi \cdot 2\alpha_k} \prod_{k=1}^n (z-c)^{-2\alpha_k} \prod_{k=1}^n \Gamma(2\alpha_k) \\ &= (-1)^n e^{-i\pi \sum_{k=1}^n 2\alpha_k} \cdot (z-c)^{-\sum_{k=1}^n 2\alpha_k} \prod_{k=1}^n \Gamma(2\alpha_k) \quad (n \in Z^+, n \geq 2). \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

Continuing this process r times, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \prod_{k=1}^n \varphi_{r\alpha_k} &= \prod_{k=1}^n (-1)^k \cdot \prod_{k=1}^n e^{-i\pi \cdot r\alpha_k} \prod_{k=1}^n (z-c)^{-r\alpha_k} \prod_{k=1}^n \Gamma(r\alpha_k) \\ &= (-1)^n e^{-i\pi \sum_{k=1}^n r\alpha_k} \cdot (z-c)^{-\sum_{k=1}^n r\alpha_k} \prod_{k=1}^n \Gamma(r\alpha_k) \quad (n \in Z^+, n \geq 2). \end{aligned} \quad (2.8)$$

Again, operating $N^{\sum_{k=1}^n (1\alpha_k + 2\alpha_k + \dots + r\alpha_k)}$ to the both sides of (2.1) and using (2.4), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_{\sum_{k=1}^n (1\alpha_k + 2\alpha_k + \dots + r\alpha_k)} &= -e^{-i\pi \sum_{k=1}^n (1\alpha_k + 2\alpha_k + \dots + r\alpha_k)} \\ &\quad \times \Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n (1\alpha_k + 2\alpha_k + \dots + r\alpha_k)) (z-c)^{1-\sum_{k=1}^n (1\alpha_k + 2\alpha_k + \dots + r\alpha_k)} \\ & \left(\left| \Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n (1\alpha_k + 2\alpha_k + \dots + r\alpha_k)) \right| < \infty \right). \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

Therefore, we obtain

$$\frac{\prod_{k=1}^n (\varphi_{1\alpha_k} \cdot \varphi_{2\alpha_k} \dots \varphi_{r\alpha_k})}{\varphi_{\sum_{k=1}^n (1\alpha_k + 2\alpha_k + \dots + r\alpha_k)}} = \frac{\prod_{k=1}^n \varphi_{1\alpha_k} \cdot \prod_{k=1}^n \varphi_{2\alpha_k} \dots \prod_{k=1}^n \varphi_{r\alpha_k}}{\varphi_{\sum_{k=1}^n (1\alpha_k + 2\alpha_k + \dots + r\alpha_k)}}, \quad (2.10)$$

which on using (2.6), (2.7), (2.8) and (2.9) in the r. h. s., becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\prod_{k=1}^n (\varphi_{1\alpha_k} \cdot \varphi_{2\alpha_k} \dots \varphi_{r\alpha_k})}{\varphi_{\sum_{k=1}^n (1\alpha_k + 2\alpha_k + \dots + r\alpha_k)}} &= \frac{(-1)^n e^{-i\pi \sum_{k=1}^n 1\alpha_k} \cdot (z-c)^{-\sum_{k=1}^n 1\alpha_k} \prod_{k=1}^n \Gamma(1\alpha_k)}{-e^{-i\pi \sum_{k=1}^n (1\alpha_k + 2\alpha_k + \dots + r\alpha_k)}} \\ &\quad \times \frac{(-1)^n e^{-i\pi \sum_{k=1}^n 2\alpha_k} \cdot (z-c)^{-\sum_{k=1}^n 2\alpha_k} \prod_{k=1}^n \Gamma(2\alpha_k)}{\Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n (1\alpha_k + 2\alpha_k + \dots + r\alpha_k))} \\ &\quad \times \frac{\dots (-1)^n e^{-i\pi \sum_{k=1}^n r\alpha_k} \cdot (z-c)^{-\sum_{k=1}^n r\alpha_k} \prod_{k=1}^n \Gamma(r\alpha_k)}{(z-c)^{1-\sum_{k=1}^n (1\alpha_k + 2\alpha_k + \dots + r\alpha_k)}} \end{aligned}$$

$$= (-1)^{rn-1} \frac{\prod_{k=1}^n \Gamma({}_1\alpha_k) \times \prod_{k=1}^n \Gamma({}_2\alpha_k) \times \dots \times \prod_{k=1}^n \Gamma({}_r\alpha_k)}{\Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n ({}_1\alpha_k + {}_2\alpha_k + \dots + {}_r\alpha_k))} \quad (2.11)$$

Multiplying the r. h. s. of (2.11) by

$$\frac{\Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n {}_1\alpha_k) \Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n {}_2\alpha_k) \dots \Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n {}_r\alpha_k)}{\Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n {}_1\alpha_k) \Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n {}_2\alpha_k) \dots \Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n {}_r\alpha_k)},$$

we obtain

$$\frac{\prod_{k=1}^n (\varphi_{{}_1\alpha_k} \cdot \varphi_{{}_2\alpha_k} \dots \varphi_{{}_r\alpha_k})}{\varphi_{\sum_{k=1}^n ({}_1\alpha_k + {}_2\alpha_k + \dots + {}_r\alpha_k)}} = (-1)^{rn-1} \frac{\prod_{k=1}^n \Gamma({}_1\alpha_k) \prod_{k=1}^n \Gamma({}_2\alpha_k)}{\Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n {}_1\alpha_k) \Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n {}_2\alpha_k)} \dots \frac{\prod_{k=1}^n \Gamma({}_r\alpha_k)}{\Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n {}_r\alpha_k)} \\ \times \frac{\Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n {}_1\alpha_k) \Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n {}_2\alpha_k) \dots \Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n {}_r\alpha_k)}{\Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n ({}_1\alpha_k + {}_2\alpha_k + \dots + {}_r\alpha_k))}, \quad (2.12)$$

which on using definition (1.9) in the r. h. s., yields assertion (2.2) of Theorem 2.1, under the conditions.

Remark 2.1.

Operating N^{α_k-1} to the both sides of (2.1) and using identity (2.4) and then proceeding on the same lines of proof of Theorem (2.1), we get the following result :

Theorem 2.2.

$$\frac{\prod_{k=1}^n (\varphi_{{}_1\alpha_k-1} \cdot \varphi_{{}_2\alpha_k-1} \dots \varphi_{{}_r\alpha_k-1})}{\varphi_{\sum_{k=1}^n (({}_1\alpha_k + {}_2\alpha_k + \dots + {}_r\alpha_k) - 1)}} \\ = (z - c)^{rn-1} {}_nB({}_1\alpha_k - 1) {}_nB({}_2\alpha_k - 1) \dots {}_nB({}_r\alpha_k - 1) \\ \times B(\sum_{k=1}^n {}_1\alpha_k - 1, \sum_{k=1}^n {}_2\alpha_k - 1, \dots, \sum_{k=1}^n {}_r\alpha_k - 1), \quad (2.13)$$

where

$$|\Gamma({}_1\alpha_k - 1)|, |\Gamma({}_2\alpha_k - 1)|, \dots, |\Gamma({}_r\alpha_k - 1)| < \infty, |\Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n ({}_1\alpha_k - 1 + {}_2\alpha_k - 1 + \dots + {}_r\alpha_k - 1))| < \infty, \\ |\Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n {}_1\alpha_k - 1)|, |\Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n {}_2\alpha_k - 1)|, \dots, |\Gamma(\sum_{k=1}^n {}_r\alpha_k - 1)| < \infty \text{ and} \\ {}_1\alpha_k - 1, {}_2\alpha_k - 1, \dots, {}_r\alpha_k - 1$$

($r, k=1,2,\dots,n \in Z^+, n \geq 2$) are variables (constants for special case) with order number k .

In the next section, we derive some results for the usual Beta functions as special case of main results (2.2) and (2.13).

3. Special cases

Taking $r = 2$ in results (2.2) and (2.13), we get the following results for the usual Beta function :

$$\frac{\prod_{k=1}^n (\varphi_{1\alpha_k} \cdot \varphi_{2\alpha_k})}{\varphi_{\sum_{k=1}^n (\alpha_k + \alpha_k)}} = (-1)^{2n-1} {}_n\mathbf{B}(1\alpha_k) \times {}_n\mathbf{B}(2\alpha_k) \\ \times \mathbf{B}\left(\sum_{k=1}^n 1\alpha_k, \sum_{k=1}^n 2\alpha_k\right) \quad (3.1)$$

and

$$\frac{\prod_{k=1}^n (\varphi_{1\alpha_k-1} \cdot \varphi_{2\alpha_k-1})}{\varphi_{\sum_{k=1}^n ((1\alpha_k + 2\alpha_k) - 1)}} = (z - c)^{2n-1} {}_n\mathbf{B}(1\alpha_k - 1) {}_n\mathbf{B}(2\alpha_k - 1) \\ \times \mathbf{B}\left(\sum_{k=1}^n 1\alpha_k - 1, \sum_{k=1}^n 2\alpha_k - 1\right) \quad (3.2)$$

respectively.

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